

due to the presence of shorter conjugated chain for resonance while the compound No. 2 shows deep coloured fluorescence due to the presence of long conjugated chain for resonance (according to E. R. Watson theory of color).

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References

1. A.I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry" IIIrd Ed. 492.
2. A.I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry" IIIrd Ed. 986.
3. E. J. BELLEMY, Infrared of Organic Compounds.

Phytochemical Studies on *Salvia coccinea* Linn

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In view of the high medicinal importance and utility of *Salvia species*¹ (Family-Labiata) in various ailments such as diarrhoea, haemorrhoids, lung diseases, gangrene etc., a systematic chemical investigation of *Salvia coccinea*² Linn. on which no phytochemical work seems to have been done so far, has been undertaken in this laboratory. It is a slender herb, 1-2 ft. high; native of S. America. It also grows between 3500-7000 ft. in the West Himalayas.

The air dried powdered whole plant of *S. coccinea* (1.5 Kg.) was extracted successively with petroleum ether (60°-80°) and benzene.

Petroleum ether concentrate was subjected to chromatography over Brockmann alumina. Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (1:1) mixture yielded a compound (0.02 gm.) which on crystallisation from acetone gave a colourless solid m.p. 84°-85°. The I. R. spectrum of the solid discloses its alcoholic nature (ν_{\max} . 3300 cm^{-1} associated-OH). The mass spectrum of the compound in addition to molecular ion peak at m/e 452, exhibits ion peaks at m/e 434 (M-18) and m/e 31 (-CH₂OH). The physical properties of the compound were found to be very similar to those reported for n-hentriacontanol³ which was finally confirmed by the direct comparison (m.m.p., Co.T.L.C. & CO.I.R.) with an authentic sample of n-hentriacontanol.

Elution with benzene afforded a product (0.15 gm.) which on crystallisation from methanol gave shining white flakes, m.p. 134°-136°. It showed bluish-violet colouration with Liebermann-Burchardt test for sterol (ν_{\max} . 3560 cm^{-1} for hydroxyl and 1649 cm^{-1} for unsaturation). The mass spectrum of the compound recorded fragment ion peaks at m/e 396 (M-18), 273 (M-side chain, C₁₀H₂₁) and m/e 255 [(M-18)-side chain. i. e., C₁₀H₂₁], besides the molecular ion peak at m/e 414. It forms an acetate m.p. 128° and a benzoate, m.p. 142°. The identity of the compound as β -sitosterol has been established by m.m.p. determination, Co-T.L.C. and CO.I.R. with the authentic specimen of the compound.

Further elution with benzene furnished a very small quantity (0.005 gm.) of another crystalline solid, m.p. 210°-212°, which responds to positive Liebermann-Burchardt test for triterpene. Further characterisation of the compound was not possible due to paucity of the material.

The benzene extract on chromatography over Brockmann alumina in the usual way afforded only β -sitosterol in the benzene chloroform (1:1) eluate.

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References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R. (India), 1956, p 219.
2. D. PRAIRN, "Bengal Plants", Botanical Survey of India, Calcutta, 1963, II, 642.
3. L. HEILBURN and H. M. BUNBARY, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", London; Eyre and Spottiswoode, 1953, Vol. 3, p 1567.

Chemical Constituents of *Rumex orientalis* Bernh

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RUMEX orientalis Bernh. syn. *Rumex patiens* Linn, a native of Europe, is found in Western Himalayas from Kumaon to Kashmir. Its roots are reported to be used as purgative¹, and are known to contain some anthraquinone derivatives². A survey.